

Early Warnings, Safer Futures: The Role of Early Warning System in Mitigating The Impacts of Climate-Induced Disasters in District Charsadda

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Abstract: *Climate-induced extreme events are ever increasing global phenomena and upsets billions of people every year. Therefore, hazards-forecasting warning systems have gain universal importance. This study also examined the effectiveness of early warning systems in reducing the adverse impact of climate-induced disasters in district Charsadda. Three union councils e.g. Batagram, Mirzadher, and Tarnab, were purposively selected from each tehsil. 300 respondents (100 from each union council) were selected through snowball sampling. Interviewer-administered questionnaires were used for data collection. The findings of the study demonstrates substantial limitations in the contemporary hazards-warning systems in the study area. The data indicated that only 6 percent of the sample size have access to early warning systems, while a huge proportion (94%) remained deprive. A small percentage (0.7%) acknowledged timely warnings about climate-hazards, while major proportion (99.3%) described it untrusted and delayed. Besides, a high percentage (78.3%) declared the warning-instructions unclear and beyond their understandings. The findings highlight the inadequacy of early warning systems for hazards predicting in the study area, emphasizing the need for upgrading to boost peoples' resilience against climate-induced disasters.*

Keywords: Climate, Disaster, Early Warning Systems, Resilience

Background of the Study:

Climate-induced disasters, such as floods, droughts, heatwaves, and storms pose ample threats to mankind, affecting millions of people and their livelihoods each year around the world. Early warning systems (EWS) have appeared as a significant tool for disaster risk reduction. It contains monitoring and warning systems, warning propagation, risk awareness, communication and response competency (Erin et al., 2022). The UN Secretary General Antonio Guterres has declared early warning system for all to make sure protection of every-person on planet earth from climate-induced hazards by 2027 (Nations, 2023). He further stated that the pace of climate change is faster than us, and we might see irreversible damages, from where recovery may not possible if quick and early actions are not taken (Azam Jan,

2020). A disaster happened when vulnerability and low resilience combined with hazards and failed to reduce the expected threats (Khan, 2008) and (Richard, 2024). Evidences reveals that effective early warning systems allow disaster-vulnerable people to take essential safety measures, such as to protect their children, patients, elders, livestock, essential documents, moveable assets and evacuate people before approaching disaster. The research studies demonstrated that preventive strategies like early warning systems could better reduce the negative impacts of climate-induced disasters- a day before disaster-alert can decrease about 30% of estimated damages of any disaster. Despite its significance in disaster mitigation, about one-third population in developing countries still have no access to timely and affective early warning systems (Cornelius et al. 2023). Similarly, early warning system has been declared the cheapest disaster-coping and forecasting measure, profiting about 9 dollars to each invested dollar. In time hazard-warning allow the people to block up the houses and doors with sandbags and in worse cases evacuation from houses in time of floods, while takes measures to avoid heatwave, droughts etc.(Travis, 2013).

The early warnings for hazards has a long history and different people used it differently in various part of the world. For example, in old days and even now in some remote rural communities, disaster forecasting and emergency responses methods are mostly remembered through knowledge exchange and stories among local people. They used plant phenology, sky colour, rivers flows, animal and birds behavior for predicting expected hazards (Annequin, 2022). Subsequently, flood susceptibility, Hydrologic Engineering Center River Analysis systems, loudspeakers, sirens, radio, TV, advertisements, booklets, newspapers, events, websites and mobile are used as early warning tools (Carter, 2010) and (Shahab et al., 2020). Similarly, due to frequent floods, in Netherlands “live with Water” program was initiated as early warning system. Through this program they disseminate the early warnings about expected hazards through mass media. These awareness measures got huge success in term of reducing disasters impacts on vulnerable people (Carter, 2010). Subsequently, in Chile before starting rainy season, the “Municipal Emergency Department” broadcast bulletins through radio about heavy rains prediction. It remind the vulnerable people to strengthen and repair doors, windows, roofs, remove debris from water channels and lawns to escape flood-water, store food, drinking water, batteries, first aid and other necessary gears (Ashfaq, 2023). Moreover, in disaster-prone country like Bangladesh, through reliable and timely early warning systems, the damages and casualties from floods and storms reduced by 100 fold in the last four decades (Christina, 2018) and (Muhammad Kaleem B. S., 2022).

Pakistan is among the high-risk country to climate-induced disasters, like droughts, floods, storms, landslides and heatwaves. With every passing day, the frequency and intensity of these disasters are in rise, taking people lives, injuring them, damaging infrastructure, eroding livelihoods and left the economy tumble down (Harbi, 2018) and (Khattak, 2016). Unfortunately, despite severe vulnerability to climate-disasters, a critical gap has been observed in technical and technological capability to monitor the status of glaciers hydrological monitoring and hazards-forecasting in Pakistan. The available hazards warning systems often fail to forecast the hazards-risks and disseminate accurate and timely early warnings (UNDP, 2023) and (BS Khattak, 2016) (Bahadar Sher Khattak, 2016)

Climate-induced disasters particularly flash floods often happened in extremely disconnected rural areas and remote hilly areas of Pakistan. Usually, predicting flash floods are very difficult because it happened in very little time and small area. Therefore its socio-economic impacts are mostly devastating (Zahid, 2024) and (Muhammad Kaleem, 2016).

Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is also a high-risk and climate-hazards prone province of Pakistan. Particularly the river-in floods, flash floods, cloud burst and glacial lake out-burst brings severe devastation almost every year. These extreme climate events have imprinted huge human, economic and social implications on the people of the province. Despite of extreme vulnerability to climate change, the hazards forecasting mechanism in the province is over-dated and inadequate. There are only seven river gauging telemetry systems of WAPDA and some basic early warning gauging systems of irrigation department are installed at different points along rivers, which reduced its forecasting capacity and timing. For real time correct floods forecasting, more than 100 devices are required to be installed on different points to disseminate early warnings well-before the disasters reaching (PDMA, 2022) and (BS Khattak, 2020). (Bahadar Sher, 2020)

The latest case is the shattering cloudbursts, heavy precipitation and devastating flash floods came about in several districts of the province like Swabi, Buner, Swat and Bajaur in August 2025. The Provincial Disaster Management Authority (PDMA) informed, that 427 people died, thousands injured, thousands of houses destroyed and local people received vast economic and infrastructural losses. Just in Buner district 291 deaths confirmed, while 1398 houses shattered, in which 1030 partly and 368 houses reported fully demolished (PDMA, 2025)

Charsadda is considered a high-risk district of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province to climate-induced disasters and one of the 11 high-risk district to floods in the country. The district is a

gateway to cloud/glacial burst, snow melting and heavy rainfall metrological events in the north-west mountains of the province-as river swat and river Kabul passes through district Charsadda, therefore the district experienced high floods in monsoon seasons almost every year. The floods of 2010 and 2020 extremely dented the human, social and economic capital of the district. Though, the river gauging telemetry systems of WAPDA and irrigation department are available in the district but they failed in disaster forecasting and real time information dissemination. Like floods, district Charsadda is also vulnerable to other climate change extreme events, such as drought, heatwave, and storms, but for early prediction these hazards, there is no such mechanism available, to allow people to prepare for and respond to these extreme events and reduce their adversities (PDMA, 2022).

It is therefore, the present study has provided an insight about the disasters forecasting early warning systems and their role in mitigating the impacts of these disasters. This study also provided suggestions and recommendations to policy makers, to install advance and reliable early warning systems in the disaster-prone areas of the district and support the local vulnerable people in preparing and responding to expected disasters well-before their happening. This study is unique in nature, as it is solely about disaster-forecasting early warning systems in the district.

Material and Methods

Charsadda is a high disaster-risk district of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa particularly to floods. The whole district was selected purposively as the universe of this study. In the next phase of sampling, the district was divided into all three tehsil-clusters e.g. Charsadda, Tangi and Shabqadar, one cluster consist one tehsil. In the third step of sampling, one union council from each cluster (Union council Mirzadher from tehsil Tangi, Tarnab from tehsil Charsadda, Tangi and Batagram from Shabqadar) was purposively selected. At 4th phase of sampling, 300 respondents (150 male and 150 female), 100 (50 male and 50 female) from each union council were purposively selected through snowball sampling method and data were collected through pre-tested interviewer-guided questionnaire. Later on the data were tabulated and analyzed through SPSS. For knowing the association and relationship between variables, Chi-square and Gamma statistics were used.

Results and Discussion

Table 1.1. Hazards Early Warning Tools:

Tool Name	Yes	No	Yes (%)	No (%)

Television Availability	240	60	80.0	20.0
Radio Availability	121	179	40.3	59.7
Smartphone with internet facility	159	141	53.0	47.0
Loudspeaker Availability	130	170	43.3	56.7
Siren etc. Availability	00	300	00	100

This table provides the details about the tools used for early warnings before and during climate-induced hazards. According to tabulated data a good proportion (80%) have the televisions in their houses, 40.3 percent owned radio and 53 percent possessed smartphones with internet facilities. A chunk (43.3%) have access to loudspeakers in the Mosques and none of the respondent reported emergency siren availability in the area for pre-hazard warnings. Early warning systems paly major role in disaster-preparedness by disseminating early warnings of upcoming climate-hazards and reducing its impacts particularly in vulnerable communities. This is align with Travis, (2013), he pointed out that effective and timely early warning about upcoming hazards enhance the resilience of vulnerable people. The data in the table indicates that in the study area still large number of people have no access to reliable and timely earning warnings and are vulnerable to climate-induced disasters. Similarly, Cornelius et al. 2023 also revealed that non-availability of reliable and timely early warning systems, increase the risks of damages in already hazards vulnerable areas. Besides, Gatiso, 2015 observed that absence of forecasting hazards early warning systems convert the hazards in disasters. Therefore they stressed information and communication technology (ICT) access as important for adaptive behaviors.

Table 1.2 Access to Early Warning Systems

Statement	Yes (Count)	No (Count)	Yes (%)	No (%)
1. Availability of governmental early warning systems in your area.	18	282	6.0	94.0
2. Access to early warnings through TV, Radio, Mobile etc.	19	281	6.3	93.7
3. Receive in time early warnings well-before Disasters.	2	298	0.7	99.3

4. Understand the guidelines provided in early-warning messages.	65	235	21.7	78.3
5. Government early warnings contain clear evacuation guidelines in selected emergency camps.	4	296	1.3	98.7
6. Acted on a warning in the past (e.g., storing supplies, evacuation).	0	300	0.0	100.0
7. Once received an early warning, passed it on to others.	178	122	59.3	40.7
8. The community have an organized plan to spread timely early warnings about approaching disasters.	0	300	0.0	100.0
9. The neighbors also have access and trust official-warnings.	45	255	15.0	85.0
10. Women also have access and disseminate upcoming disaster early warnings.	23	277	7.7	92.3

The above table demonstrates the details about respondents' access to climate-hazards early warning systems in the study area. The data shows that tiny percentage (6%) have access to

early warning systems and large portion (94%) reported non-availability of effective and reliable early warning systems. The table further reveals that a very small size (0.7%) received timely early warnings of climate-hazards but a large percentage (99.3%) reported delayed and incorrect hazards-warnings. Moreover, only 21.7 percent of the respondents reported the understating of guidelines provided in early warning messages, while a huge population size (78.3%) were unable to understand the provided instructions in the early warning messages. Subsequently, a small proportion (1.3%) acknowledged clear evacuation instructions to designated emergency campus in government early warning messages, while huge portion (98.7%) refused clear instructions. The entire (100%) population size never acted upon early warnings in the past. About (59.3%) of respondents pass on the received early warnings to neighbors and 40.7 percent of them do not disseminate to others. The whole sample size (100%) reported no organized early warning systems availability in the study area. These findings are aligned with Shrestha et al. 2021, according to them, in entire South Asia, the hazards-forecasting systems are inadequate, weak, and delayed hazards information and communication leave the vulnerable people unprotected during disasters. Moreover, 15 percent of the respondents admitted that their neighbors also receive and trust official hazards early warnings, while huge portion (85%) of them not agreed with the statement. In the same manner, only small portion (7.7%) agreed that women also receive and disseminate hazards early warning in the study areas, while large sample size (92.3%) refused the statement. Saigal and Srivastava, 2025, and Daoud, 2021 observed that exclusion of such a huge number of women from disaster preparedness process, spoil the efforts of community resilience and reduction of disaster damages.

The explained data demonstrate that in the study area, the early warning systems for climate-hazards forecasting are inadequate and mostly disseminate delayed hazards warnings. Majority of the people in the study area have not access to and nor taken benefits from it. That's why, they always received huge damages in every disaster they experienced and they are constantly at risk to future floods. This data findings is aligned with Erin et al. 2022, he also demonstrated that reliable and timely forecasting climate-hazards can allow the vulnerable people to prepare and response to hazards in advance and reduce its damages. It enable vulnerable people to move movable assets and vulnerable family members to safe places. Therefore, these patterns suggest a manifold communication breakdown— early warnings are not only inadequate and delayed but also lack inclusivity, accessibility and clarity. Marrero, 2010 also emphasized the urgent need for culturally appropriate, localized, and people-friendly early warning systems

that incorporate several communication channels, actionable instructions and gender-inclusive outreaches. Lacking such hazards forecasting warnings systems might sustain people vulnerability to climate-induced disasters.

Table 1.3 Adaptive Capacity and Resilience Building through Early Warning System

Statement	To Less Extent	To Some Extent	Neutral	To Great Extent
Aware of steps which can be taken, to prepare for floods/disasters after receiving early warnings.	20	20	255	5
Received information about disaster preparedness through radio, TV, SMS, speaker, siren or community sessions.	30	25	230	15
Rely on traditional weather signals (sky color, abrupt weather change, animal behavior, rise in rivers etc.)	85	80	120	15
Timely access to early warning systems.	40	10	245	5
Received training from NGOs or government on how to respond to disasters-early warnings.	0	0	300	0
Trust the early warning alerts, receive on phone or radio etc.	20	20	255	5
The family is better prepared for disasters now than five years ago because of timely warnings.	20	5	275	0
Early warnings help in agricultural adaptation and resilience	30	20	245	5
Early warnings help in physical adaptation and resilience	20	10	270	0
Where to go or whom to contact in case of a disaster-warnings, particularly floods.	10	5	285	0

Women also become resilient after early warnings	10	2	288	0
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This table gives the details about the role of early warning systems in disaster preparedness in the study area. A small number (20n) each to less and some extent knows about step of disaster preparedness after receiving hazard-warnings to less and some extent. Only 5 respondents prepared level was to great extent, while a huge population size (255n) got no benefits from early warnings. Through, radio, TV, SMS etc. 30n respondents receive the early warnings to less and 25n to some extent and 15n to great extent. A huge number (230n) have no access to early warnings of hazards in the study area. A good number (85n) and 80n respectively follow the traditional weather signals to less and some extent. A small number (15n) follow it to great extent and 120n denied traditional weather signals. Moreover, 40n and 10n of sample size have access to timely early warnings to less and some extent respectively. A tiny portion (5n) reported to great extent access and a huge number (245n) have no access to timely hazard-warnings. All the 300n respondents denied any training about early warnings by government/NGOs in the study area. Very few number (20n) agreed to less and some extent and 5n to great extent about trust on received early warning alerts for resilience building, while large number (245n) remained neutral. Similarly, 20n and 5n considered the present hazards-early warnings helpful in resilience building and huge number (275n) stayed neutral. Subsequently, a very small number (30n), (20n) and (5n) of the total population size admitted the role of contemporary early earnings system in agriculture adaptation and resilience to less, some and great extent respectively, while majority (245n) refused the statement. In the same manner, only 20n and 10n of respondents accepted the available early warning systems in physical adaptation and resilience to less and some extent respectively, while large population size (270n) denied its role in the process. Furthermore, tiny portion of sample size (10n) and (5n) have to less and some extent idea, that where to go after receiving the hazard alerts, while bulk (285n) were clueless in this regard. About women adaptation and resilience after receiving hazard-warning, only 10n and 2n support the statement, and majority (288n) denied it. This data presentation indicates that the hazard-early warning systems in the study area are inadequate, delayed and not systematic. Majority of the people in the study area have no access to timely warning alerts and got no benefits in the past disasters. Therefore, Agrawal et al. 2021 revealed that when indigenous knowledge is integrated with advance scientific hazards-forecast systems, ensure accuracy, community trust and help in resilience building. Moreover, IPCC, 2022 and Leal Filho et al. 2020 demonstrated that for making the hazard-warning

systems effective and enhancing the people's resilience to climate-induced disasters, international cooperation, climate-finance and technology transfer are inevitable. Adger et al. 2020 called, biased, inadequate and delayed assistance as maladaptation, because such interventions exacerbate vulnerability by eliminating those most in need.

Results and Discussion:

Table 1.4 Association between early warning access and adaptive capacity

Early Warning System		Adaptive Capacity			Frequency	Statistical Measures
Indicators	Responses	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Total	Statistics
Participation in EW training	Agree	120	48	18	186	$\chi^2=49.860$
	Disagree	24	22	38	84	p=0.000
	Uncertain	18	6	6	30	
Response plan at household level	Agree	114	45	19	178	$\chi^2=35.693$
	Disagree	30	32	35	97	p=0.000
	Uncertain	11	7	7	25	
emergency-bag readiness	Agree	95	64	17	176	$\chi^2=55.629$
	Disagree	25	22	46	93	p=0.000
	Uncertain	13	12	6	31	
Shelter location awareness	Agree	114	55	15	184	$\chi^2=56.386$
	Disagree	22	32	38	92	p=0.000
	Uncertain	9	11	4	24	

The data analysis in table no.1.4, demonstrates that access to hazards early warning significantly increases adaptive capacity of hazard-vulnerable people. The analyzed data shows entirely significant statistical associations ($p=0.000$), with chi-square values ranging from 35.693 to 56.386. Participation in early warning trainings, response plans at household level, emergency-bag readiness, and shelter location awareness were significantly supported, with shelter location awareness ($\chi^2=56.386$) indicating the uppermost influence. The high levels of agreement in all variables recommend that hazard-preparedness measures resulting from early warning systems directly transform into adaptive behaviors, strengthening resilience both at the household and community levels. Cornelius, 2023 also observed that timely and accurate hazards alerts allow vulnerable people to prepare and respond to approaching hazards. So effective hazards forecasting systems enhance adaptive capacity of people.

Table 1.5 Association between early warning access and community resilience

Early Warning System		Community Resilience			Frequency	Statistical Measures
Indicators	Responses	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Total	Statistics
Early-warnings through SMS	Agree	114	59	17	190	$\chi^2=37.391$
	Disagree	30	25	31	86	$p=0.000$
	Uncertain	14	2	8	24	
Through Radio/TV	Agree	108	45	32	185	$\chi^2=19.729$
	Disagree	31	20	35	86	$p=0.001$
	Uncertain	14	9	6	29	
Access to siren	Agree	111	48	20	179	$\chi^2=25.802$
	Disagree	35	28	33	96	$p=0.000$
	Uncertain	11	8	6	25	
Trust on Forecast	Agree	107	49	18	174	$\chi^2=41.233$
	Disagree	30	30	41	101	$p=0.000$

	Uncertain	14	7	4	25	
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Lead time adequacy	Agree	113	44	25	182	$\chi^2=54.798$
	Disagree	24	18	50	92	p=0.000
	Uncertain	16	4	6	26	
Message clarity	Agree	107	46	24	177	$\chi^2=15.649$
	Disagree	37	34	25	96	p=0.004
	Uncertain	16	4	7	27	
Alert frequency sufficiency	Agree	128	45	12	185	$\chi^2=56.823$
	Disagree	26	24	32	82	p=0.000
	Uncertain	11	14	8	33	
Evacuation info disposal	Agree	107	39	27	173	$\chi^2=18.313$
	Disagree	36	32	31	99	p=0.001
	Uncertain	12	9	7	28	

Findings in table no.1.5 indicate that access to disaster-early forecasting has an important positive association with vulnerable communities' resilience, with all chi-square values statistically significant ($p \leq 0.001$). Early warnings through SMS ($\chi^2=37.391$), through radio/TV, through sirens, and trust on forecast, Lead time adequacy all demonstrated strong associations, with the highest being alert frequency sufficiency ($\chi^2=56.823$). Maximum respondents approved that effective and timely early warning tools improved resilience, though impartiality and difference highlight persisting encounters in reporting, consistency, and trust. Together, the results show that timely and reliable hazard-warning systems are crucial in supporting proactive community responses. These findings aligned with Azhar, 2020 results, he also indicated that hazards early alerts directly influence community resilience and can reduce damages of disasters.

The findings of the study demonstrates that timely and effective early warning systems, allow the vulnerable people to prepare and respond to expected disaster. A systematic and reliable early warning system enhances resilience of vulnerable people and reduce the intensity of disaster impacts on them. Unfortunately, in the study area, it was observed that the hazard-forecasting systems was inadequate, over-dated and delayed. Majority of the respondents have no access to timely early warnings. Therefore, they were found extremely vulnerable to future climate-induced hazards.

Conclusion:

The findings of this study demonstrates that hazard-forecasting systems in district Charsadda are extremely inadequate, delayed and ineffective. The findings revealed that only 6 percent of people in the study area are reported access to early warning systems, and a huge proportion (99.3%) declared the contemporary warning system over-dated, untrusted and delayed. A major percentage (78.3%) reported that early warnings consist no clear evacuation and safety measures, it mostly beyond our understandings, which further enhances their vulnerability to escalating climate-induced disasters. The most worse is, that only 7.7 percent respondents admitted that women also receive and disseminate hazards-alerts. All the (100%) respondents denied the presence of an organized early warning system in the study area and their common distrust in official hazard-warnings demand immediate consideration. Installing and enhancing the effectiveness of hazards-forecasting warning systems in the disaster-prone district of Charsadda is not only a requirement but vital for fostering resilience to future-disasters against the backdrop of growing climate-induced disasters. Therefore, it is highly recommended that hazard-warning systems needs upgradation and expansion to all disaster-prone areas of district Charsadda to protect lives, livelihoods and infrastructure from future disasters.

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